

Antioxidative effect of polyphenols present in corn (*Zea mays* L.)

Deblina Roy^a, Ranjana Das^b, Sibani Chakraborty^a, Mahua Ghosh^b and Santinath Ghosh^{b*}

^aDepartment of Home Science, University of Calcutta, 20B, Judges Court Road, Kolkata-700 027, India

^bDepartment of Chemical Technology, University of Calcutta, 92, Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Kolkata-700 009, India

E-mail : santinathghosh@yahoo.com.hk Fax : 91-033-23519755

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Abstract : The polyphenol content in baby corn as well as in mature corn and their *in vitro* antioxidant activity have been studied. Mature corn and baby corn when extracted with 80% methanol, contained about 0.79 and 0.35 g polyphenol per 100 g (as gallic acid equivalent) dry matter respectively. Both the polyphenols have shown strong reducing activity, hydroxy radical scavenging activity, lipid oxidation inhibiting activity and prolonged ABTS^{•+} radical cation scavenging activity. This observation will be beneficial in application of the corn extracts in extended product self life. The result of the study indicates that corn is rich in active polyphenolic antioxidants, which are very much important from nutritional point of view.

Keywords : Antioxidant, polyphenol.

A large body of research is now involved in investigating the compounds that are active in conferring protection against major diseases for improving quality of life in a non-pharmacological way. Natural antioxidants are more preferred than synthetic antioxidants, which are associated with some ill effects¹. Phenolic compounds are natural phytochemicals, well known for their antioxidant property and are mostly found in fruits, vegetables, oil seeds², sea weeds³ and beans⁴.

Corn (*Zea mays* L.) is a well-known cereal in India. Its production in India is next to rice, wheat and jowar. Corn grains are good source of Vitamin E, easily digested carbohydrate (66.2%), fat (3.6%) and proteins (11.1%). Baby corn is also gaining special attraction due to presence of natural fibre as well as nutritious components. Few reports however, have addressed the antioxidant activity of corn product⁵. In the present study our objective is to determine the polyphenol content in matured corn as well as in baby corn and antioxidative efficiency of the polyphenol extract by various *in vitro* methods.

Results and discussion

Table 1 shows the polyphenol content of both baby corn and matured corn (before and after defatting), extracted with 80% methanol and 80% ethanol⁶. The

Table 1. Total polyphenol content (expressed as gallic acid equivalent)

Name of raw materials	In 80% methanol	In 80% ethanol
Baby corn (Before defatted)	0.5064	0.6154
Matured corn (Before defatted)	0.1340	0.1650
Baby corn (After defatted)	0.6275	0.7922
Matured corn (After defatted)	0.3083	0.3539

polyphenol content has increased significantly after defatting in both baby and matured corn. In case of baby corn, after defatting, polyphenol content increased marginally, due to very low oil content in baby corn. Baby corn contain higher amount of polyphenols than matured corn and this is mainly due to utilization of whole baby corn instead of grains. Results show that the polyphenols are better extracted in 80% ethanol compared to 80% methanol and 80% ethanol was used as extraction medium of corn polyphenolic components.

Reducing activity : Reducing activity of the corn extract was expressed as ascorbic acid equivalents from the

ascorbic acid calibration curve according to the method of Yen and Chen⁷. Result shows that, one mg of ascorbic acid is equivalent to 0.8445 mg of baby corn and 4.651 mg of matured corn. These results suggest that baby corn polyphenols have higher reducing activity compared to matured corn polyphenols on the basis of their *in vitro* reducing activity. This difference in antioxidant activity may be due to the extraction of polyphenol from the whole baby corn.

Hydroxyl radical scavenging activity : In biological system, hydroxyl radical is capable of damaging almost every molecule found in living cells. It is considered to be one of the quick initiators of the lipid peroxidation process. The hydroxyl radical scavenging activity of corn extract was determined according to the method given in literature⁸. The activity of both the extracts increase with increasing the concentration of extracts. Matured corn extract exhibit higher hydroxyl radical scavenging activity of 31.11% than that of baby corn, 24.95%. The ability of the ethanol extract in scavenging hydroxyl radical seems to be useful to prevent the propagation of lipid peroxidation.

Lipid oxidation inhibitory effect : Lipid oxidation inhibitory effect of the corn extract was done on linoleic acid emulsion according to the method of Coupland *et al.*⁹ in aqueous phase and according to the method of Recknagel and Glende¹⁰ in organic phase. Both matured corn and baby corn show good inhibition to the production of diene and thiobarbituric acid reactive substance (TBARS) (expressed as absorbance value). Initial % diene content of 0.0078 increases to 0.2547 for control (sample without polyphenol dose) where as for matured and baby corn it becomes 0.1770 and 0.1962 after 29 h of oxidation in the organic phase. Initial TBARS absorbance of 0.267 increases to 1.071 for control sample, where as for matured and baby corn it becomes 0.638 and 0.839 respectively after 29 h of oxidation in the aqueous phase. So inhibition of oxidation is clearly indicated by the corn polyphenols. Results also illustrate that polyphenols in matured corn is more effective in inhibiting the oxidation of linoleic acid both in organic phase and in aqueous phase.

ABTS^{•+} radical cation scavenging activity : ABTS^{•+} radical scavenging property reflects the ability of an antioxidant species to donate electron and hydrogen atom to inactivate these radical species. The ABTS^{•+} radical cation scavenging activity was determined according to the method of Re *et al.*¹¹. Percent inhibition of ABTS^{•+} cation with time for ascorbic acid, butylated hydroxy anisol

Fig. 1. ABTS^{•+} Radical scavenging activity of baby corn and matured corn in comparison with ascorbic acid and BHA using 1% solution for each sample : (◆) ascorbic acid, (■) BHA, (▲) baby corn, (×) matured corn.

(BHA), matured corn and baby corn are shown in Fig. 1. Concentration (mg/ml) of these four compounds required to quench 50% of the ABTS^{•+} radical cation are 1.700, 5.200, 9.930, 21.229 respectively. Result illustrates that matured corn extract has higher radical scavenging activity compared to baby corn. Both the matured and baby corn extract exhibit weaker ABTS^{•+} radical cation scavenging activity than ascorbic acid and BHA. However, the duration of the antioxidant activity for the corn extract occurred over a longer period of time compared to the shorter reaction times for ascorbic acid and BHA. This may be due to more complex reaction mechanism involving one or more secondary reactions in the quenching of the ABTS^{•+} free radicals.

In summary, ethanol extract of matured and baby corn exhibit strong reducing power, better hydroxyl radical scavenging activity and prolonged ABTS^{•+} radical scavenging activity. The prolonged period of antioxidant activity of the corn extracts may be beneficial in application of extended product self-life.

Experimental

Baby corn and matured corn (yellow variety) were purchased from local market. Ascorbic acids, trichloro acetic acid (TCA), ammonium acetate, ferric chloride (anhydrous) are supplied from E. Merck, India Limited; ABTS from Sigma Aldrich Chemical Co., USA; BHA, Folin-Ciocalteaus phenol reagent, gallic acid, Tween-20, potassium ferricyanide, ethyldiene diamine tetra acetic acid di sodium salt (EDTA) were purchased from SRL (Sisco Research Laboratory, India). All experiments are performed using double distilled water. The absorbance

Roy *et al* . Antioxidative effect of polyphenols present in corn (*Zea mays* L)

was measured in a Shimadzu (1601A) UV-Vis spectrophotometer All results are expressed as average of three determinations

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